

THE MOST APPROPRIATE APPROACH FOR TEACHING YOUNG LEARNERS

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Introduction: There is no right answer to this question, as it will depend on many factors: the age of the children, class size, the competency of the teacher, availability of resources, the school context and the framework constructed by bodies that create the educational landscape for the locality.

Should oral development precede reading and writing? There is a school of thought that suggests children learn best by hearing language being effectively modelled by skilled teachers, and having natural opportunities to use language in productive activities, before embarking on robust learning of literacy. However, the relative success of this type of approach may lie in the oral competency of the teacher and easy access to appropriate resources.

In some contexts it may make more sense to expose children early to reading, learning phonics and the explicit teaching of grammar. Clearly, it makes little sense to be teaching reading and writing in a second language beyond what has been achieved in a first language, although it may be possible for the two languages to develop at similar rates. However, older learners may have knowledge of literacy to transfer over from a stronger first language. In many contexts, schools are measured by how many children pass academic exams, which may necessitate and encourage a 'teaching to the test' mentality among teachers. However, this could mean that the more important aspects of learning are neglected.

Cameron separates learning the written language, not necessarily because she sees this as coming later in a child's development, but because the written language needs to be explicitly taught by the teacher; the process needs planning and the teacher needs to understand what is involved in doing this.

However, this does not mean that written language is divorced from spoken language, but for the young language learner, language is presented, practised and learned through speaking and listening. As the result of activities that take place in the class, children learn the meaning of words and grammar 'emerge[s] from the space between words and discourse' and supports the development of meaning.

For younger learners effective classroom strategies have traditionally involved use of songs, rhymes and traditional stories with repeated language structures. The internet can be a rich source of authentic oral models via recorded songs, talking electronic books, podcasts and video clips that help learners with pronunciation as well as acquisition and reinforcement of new vocabulary.

1. Storytelling

Storytelling is a technique of teaching English to young learners where the teacher tells a story using a story book or picture book or puppets.

There are some reasons for using storytelling to teach young learners: (1) helping children master the rhythm and sounds of the language, (2) helping children master the vocabulary and grammar of the language, (3) helping children practice Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing skills, (4) helping children learn about the world through picture books, (5) helping develop children's imagination, and (6) helping children deal with their feelings, so they can accept their own feelings and understanding other people's feeling.

2 Playing games

Game are any fun activities that give young learners chances to practice English.

One of the ways to make students actively participate in classroom is playing games.

It helps:

- arousing students' interest and motivation in participating in the lesson.
- giving students a chance to communicate meaningfully.
- making students feel less anxious as they play games with only some of their friends.
- forming students' basic skills in using the Target Language (TL). - building a learning spirit as student.

There are 9 methods of teaching

Types of teaching methods include differentiated instruction, lecture-based instruction, technology-based learning, group learning, individual learning, inquiry-based learning, kinesthetic learning, game-based learning and expeditionary learning.

With the right teaching methods, educators can create an enjoyable and productive classroom experience for students where they can learn important academic and social skills to last a lifetime. There are many frameworks that a teacher could use to support students with different interests, abilities and learning styles. If you're a teacher or professional in the education field, you might benefit from learning about new instructive strategies in the field to maximize your students' chances of success in your classroom.

Individual learning. While group projects can be exciting opportunities for students, it's also important to promote individual learning so that they can work by themselves. Assigning journal entries can be an excellent way to give students time to think through topics and develop thoughts and analyses. This is especially helpful before hosting a class discussion so class members can have ideas for what to say. Teachers can read writing assignments to reward points to students who can't participate vocally in class.

Group learnig. Segmenting students into groups is a great way to teach them skills in collaboration. While in their teams, they can discuss subjects and learn about the perspectives of others. It's important to encourage both class participation and listening skills so that students can gain these abilities for the future. Teachers can assign group presentations so students can convey information to the rest of the class, ask and answer questions and interact with each other.

Game-based learning. If you want to update your classroom techniques and help children to be more excited about learning, consider developing and implementing educational games or challenges, whether in-person or online.

These can inspire children, especially kinesthetic learners, to participate more fully in the learning process and keep them motivated and focused on lessons. It can also allow them the opportunity to solve problems and reach a goal.

Expeditionary learning. Expeditionary learning is the process of learning through participating in practical experiences. These can be projects, case studies or lab experiments in the classroom or field trips to places around your school and community. For example, in a science class, you might take a trip to a nearby nature center to learn about the types of animals and plants in your area. This type of approach encourages students to apply classroom knowledge and skills to the real world. It can help them comprehend the purpose of their efforts and return to schoolwork with enthusiasm.

In this article, we define what teaching methods are, explore nine types of teaching methods, review the benefits of these methods and provide some tips for doing so successfully.

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